

α -Oximinoacetoacetarylamine Salicylhydrazones as Gravimetric Reagents for Palladium(II)

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SURVEY of the literature reveals that Pd(II) has been estimated gravimetrically using various reagents viz., dioximes of α -diketones, α -ketoaldehydes and monoximes of salicylaldehyde and furfural in the absence and presence of other metal ions¹. However, meagre work has been done on the gravimetric estimation of Pd(II) using oximinohydrazones as reagents^{2,3}. During our studies on acetoacetarylamine, we synthesised α -oximinoacetoacetarylamine salicylhydrazones⁴. In continuation of our work^{2,3}, we report here the analytical aspects of salicylhydrazones of acetoacetanilide and acetoacet-*o*-toluidide with Pd(II).

Experimental

The preparation of salicylhydrazones of α -oximinoacetoacetanilide(I) and α -oximinoacetoacet-*o*-toluidide(II) has been reported.⁴

Palladium chelate of the α -oximinoacetoacetanilide salicylhydrazone :

Palladium chloride solution in aqueous hydrochloric acid (0.05 *M*, 10 ml) was gradually added to alcoholic solution of α -oximinoacetoacetanilide salicylhydrazone (2%, 25 ml). The mixture was diluted to about 100 ml with distilled water and digested on the water bath for about half an hour; the precipitates obtained were filtered, washed with hot water and dilute alcohol and dried at 110°.

The palladium chelate of α -oximinoacetoacet-*o*-toluidide salicylhydrazone was prepared, washed and dried as above.

The colour, m.p. and composition of the chelates are respectively :

- I. Bright yellow; 307° (d); (Found : Pd, 13.45; N, 14.16%; Calc. for Pd(C₁₇H₁₅O₄N₄)₂ : Pd, 13.60; N, 14.27%).
- II. Bright yellow; 303° (d); (Found : Pd, 13.13; N, 13.92%; Calc. for Pd(C₁₈H₁₇O₄N₄)₂ : Pd, 13.12; N, 13.78%).

The chelates are found to be insoluble in common organic solvents viz., alcohols, chloroform, acetone, carbontetrachloride, benzene and acetonitrile.

Analytical procedure :

Reagents : 1% ethanolic solution of α -oximinoacetoacetarylamine salicylhydrazones (where aryl = -C₆H₅, and -C₆H₄CH₃(*o*)).

Palladium chloride solution (1.147 × 10⁻² M) :

Palladium chloride was dissolved in a 2 ml hot concentrated hydrochloric acid and diluted with distilled water to a definite volume. Palladium contents of the solution was determined by dimethylglyoxime method⁵. Solutions of copper chloride (1 × 10⁻² *M*) and nickel chloride (1.073 × 10⁻² *M*) were prepared and standardised with EDTA and dimethylglyoxime respectively.

(A) 5 ml palladium chloride solution (1.147 × 10⁻² *M*) was diluted to about 25 ml with distilled water and acidified with about 5 ml conc. hydrochloric acid. To this solution a sufficient excess of ethanolic solution of the reagent (1%, 5 ml) was added. The precipitates were digested on water bath for half an hour and filtered through a weighed sintered glass crucible (G₃), washed with hot water and aqueous ethanol (1:1) and dried at 110° to a constant weight.

(B) *Gravimetric determination of Pd(II) at different pH :* In order to study the pH ranges over which palladium could be completely precipitated by these reagents, the determination was carried out in solutions at different pH adjusted by using dilute hydrochloric acid or dilute sodium hydroxide solution. The pH range was found to be 0.4 to 9.0.

Results and Discussion

The results show that Pd(II) could be quantitatively estimated over a wide pH range, 0.7 to 9.0 in the absence of other metal ions. The pH values of incipient precipitation for metal ions viz., Cu(II), Ni(II), Fe(II) and Fe(III) suggest that in the presence of such metal ions palladium(II) could be estimated below pH 3. The detail study of quantitative estimation of palladium in presence of Cu(II) and Ni(II) has shown that Pd(II) could be estimated quantitatively in the pH range 0.5 to 0.9.

Complete precipitation, insolubility in common organic solvents and easy filtration of the complexes favour the use of these reagents as good gravimetric reagents for Pd(II). These characteristics are comparable with those of the standard method for the determination of palladium with dimethylglyoxime.⁵

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References

1. F. J. WELCHER, "Organic Analytical Reagents", D. Van Nostrand Co., Inc., New York, 1962, Vol. III.
2. M. R. PATEL and B. N. MANKAD, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1968, **31**, 32.
3. M. M. PATEL, M. R. PATEL and B. N. MANKAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 318.
4. M. R. PATEL and B. N. MANKAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **41**, 841.
5. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans, Green & Co., London, Second Edition, 1960, p. 445.

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